

Metagenomic Exploration Microbial Diversity of Industrial Effluent Contaminated Soils of Silvassa, India

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Abstract: This study reports a metagenomic approach, to investigate the microbial diversity of soils contaminated with different industrial effluents. Three different contaminated soil samples were collected from different industrial sites or Rakholi, Surangi and Kherdi, in Silvassa region. Total soil DNA was extracted and whole genome sequencing Library was prepared and amplified using universal primers. The genomic library was quantified and validated by Qubit and 4150 TapeStation system, followed by sequencing and bioinformatic analysis of metagenome, to identify microbial diversity in the contaminated soil. Microbial diversity analysis represented the dominance of Pseudomonadota, Actinomycetota, Bacillota, Myxococcota, Acidobacteriota and Thermodesulfobacteriota in all the three metagenomes. Presence of pollutant degrading microbes such as Bacillus, Clostridium, Candidatus Entothionella, Pseudomonas and Desulfomonas strongly indicates their bioremediation ability. KEGG and COG annotated main functional categories included carbohydrate metabolism, amino acids metabolism, and protein metabolism. This study explored the still unexplored soil bacterial diversity, through metagenomic approach, and is the first ever report for the region of Silvassa, Dadra & Nagar Haveli, India. Further deep investigation shall reveal novel species or proteins produced by microbial community, with potential applications towards sustainable environment.

Keywords: COG, KEGG, Metagenomes, Microbial Diversity, Next generation sequencing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Microorganisms are the most diverse group of organisms present everywhere on the earth, including soil, water, human gut and solid waste (Singh et al., 2022). 1 g of soil predictably contains 10^{30} microorganisms and thousands of archaea and eukaryotes (Whitman et al., 1998). Usually, the soil microbial diversity is known as very complex structure and it is very difficult for exploratory research. On the basis of advance research in field of microbial science, about 1% of bacterial species in environment are found to be culturable (Amann et al., 1995; Handelsman, 2004). Culture-based approaches are unable to completely characterize the microbial diversity of soil. As metagenomic approach is a culture-independent approach, is easily applicable to explain the complete microbial diversity of soil, water, gut microbiome, wastewater, etc. (Rajendhran & Gunasekaran, 2008). Metagenomic sequencing analyze the microbial diversity by direct analyzing the genetic material (DNA) isolated from the given habitats.

Richness and diversified soil flora play crucial role in soil health. Thus, presence of contaminants or pollutants in soil affects the dynamic interaction of microbial community and their ecological functions (Yan et al., 2021 and Y. Q. Li et al., 2023). A strong co-relation exists amongst the soil microorganisms and the environmental conditions, which includes presence or absence of biotic and abiotic factors (Q. Li et al., 2020). Various physiochemical factors govern the microbial population in soil, including soil pH, moisture content, organic carbon content, and nutrient content, and they also depend on various factors such as climate, land use, management and seasons (Lüneberg et al., 2018). Therefore, the diversity of microbial community is directly related to the structure and function of the ecosystem (Peng et al., 2015a). However, it is observed that at times, the microbial population is different even under the same climate condition such variation can be observed due the change in biotic and abiotic factors in ecosystem, which helps using the quality of bacterial population, as a microbial indicator of soil quality (B. Wang et al., 2020; Z. Yu et al., 2021).

Functional expression of microbial community is the direct indication of the flora and fauna of soil. Upon release of pollutants, drastic effects are observed in the structure and metabolism of the microbial community (Koshlaf et al., 2020). Decontamination of petroleum-based pollutants can be done using chemical and biological methods, wherein, the biological methods, involving microbial decontamination, are cheaper and more effective for crude-oil based contaminants (Y. Yu et al., 2020; Lopez et al., 2022). These biological methods are also known as bioremediation (Ojuederie & Babalola, 2017; Y. Yu et al., 2020). Currently, with advances in Molecular biology researches, these bioremediation techniques are combined with 'omics' approaches to identify the culturable and non-culturable bacteria and fungi, involved in degradation process of such contaminants and assisting soil health restoration (Elufisan et al., 2019; Cabral et al., 2022).

Prime focus of the current studies has been used for the analysis of microbial diversity and their function in the industrial effluent contaminated soil. However, majority report indicates that the alteration in microbial population is due to different industrial effluent contamination in soil, including oils, industrial waste water, petroleum content, pharmaceutical waste, agricultural waste etc. (Auti et al., 2019). Recently, investigators are also exploring the comparative analysis of microbiome data of contaminated and normal soils, with reference to factors, such as, effect of environmental factors and treatment uses for the restoration of that site to analyze the functional diversity of microbial population in normal soil and contaminated soil (Auti et al., 2019). For example, in crude oil contamination the dominance of selective microbial population compares to uncontaminated soil occurs which allows the growth of more diverse bacterial population in contaminated soil (Peng et al., 2015b; Sun et al., 2015; Abbasian et al., 2016).

Normally the biodegradation and removal of such pollutant can be removed by indigenous microbes also known as primary mechanism for attenuation of contaminants, but this is not enough to restoration of soil and complete removal of such contaminants. Bioaugmentation and phytoremediation are the more efficient mechanisms used for the restoration (Bento et al., 2005; Suja et al., 2014). Still, the restoration of such contaminated sites is very challenging and relies on newer technologies. Now are days new approaches being use such as in silico and ex silico analysis.

Recent advances in molecular technologies such as development of next generation sequencing (NGS) reveals the many aspects that are highly essential for the quantification, identification and analysis of microbial population in soil (Shar et al., 2021; M. Wang, Zhao, et al., 2021). The NGS based approaches such as Illumina sequencing were used for the determination of most dominant microbial phyla in contaminated soil. It is observed that the most abundant species were belonging to the phyla such as Proteobacteria, Firmicutes, Bacteroidetes (Shahi et al., 2016). Researchers also used 16S rRNA gene-based Illumina MiSeq sequencing for the analysis of microbial community of oil contaminated soil in which they found that the proteobacteria (49.11%) and actinobacteria (24.24%) were the most abundant phyla and the major genera were Pseudoxanthomonas, Luteimonas, Alkanindiges, Acinetobacter and Agromyces (Zhang et al., 2010).

Previous studies of soil using NGS techniques reveals that it is an important tool for study of microbial diversity and their functional role in different habitats (Chopkova et al., 2023; Kulik et al., 2023). In current study, the analysis of microbial population and diversity in the industrial effluent contaminated soil, using metagenomic approach, based on NGS technique, to reveal the microbial community structure, as influenced by the environmental factors.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Soil samples collection

Three different soil samples were collected from three different industrial sites of Dadra and Nagar Haveli, India. The soil sample collection sites were designated as SA1, SA2 and SA3, and the industrial effluent contaminated soil was sampled in triplicate from idle soil and without plants. SA1 samples were collected from dumpsite of Castrol Lubricant Pvt. Ltd., Rakholi, D&NH, Silvassa, (20.226488°N and 73.037310°E). SA2 samples were collected from dumpsites of Surangi Industrial Zone, Surangi, D&NH (20.156894°N and 73.013594°E), While SA3 samples were collected from H. P. Industry Ltd., Kherdi, D&NH. (20.102512°N and 73.023199°E). (Fig.1) All three samples were collected by removing the topsoil (around 0 to 5 cm), gathering approximately 500 g of soil, at a depth of 5 to 10 cm and then immediately transferring the samples into sterile plastic containers that were kept in ice box and transfer in the laboratory. The triplicates soil sample were pooled to form major three soil samples, as per the protocols from literature (Gazaka et al. 2001). Half of the soil was immediately stored at -80 °C and remaining soil sample were process for molecular analysis.

Figure 1. Locations of soil sample collection sites (a) SA1: Dumpsite of Castrol Lubricant Pvt. Ltd., Rakholi, D&NH, Silvassa, (b) SA2: Dumpsite of Surangi Industrial Zone, Surangi, D & N. H. and (c) SA3: Dumpsite of H.P Industry Ltd., Kherdi, D & N. H.

2.2. DNA Extraction and Quantification:

DNA extraction was carried out using DNeasy Power Soil Pro Kit protocol and eluted with 25 μ l of Nuclease free water (DNeasy PowerSoil Pro kit). DNA concentrations were determined by using Qubit™ 1X ds DNA HS Assay Kit (Thermo-Fisher Scientific), which contains dye as well as buffer and two standards. Qubit reagent contains one of the most sensitive dyes, which will accurately quantify only the double stranded DNA molecules and evaluated with 2% agarose gel. (Fig.S1)

Dye and the buffer were diluted at 1:200 ratio and 199 μ l of the working solution was transferred into a Qubit™ Assay Tube (Catalog: Q32856, Thermo Fisher Scientific) to which 1 μ l of the DNA sample was mixed, vortexed and incubated at room temperature (RT) for 2 minutes. The final volume in each tube would be 200 μ L. The readings were taken in a Qubit 3.0 Fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The concentration of the samples presented in Table S1.

2.3. Library Preparation and Quantification

Whole-Genome sequencing (WGS) library was prepared using QIAseq FX DNA Library Kit for Illumina (Catalog: 180479, QIAGEN). In brief, 150 ng of DNA is directly end repaired and an “A” is added to the 3’ ends during the FX reaction, making the DNA fragments ready for adapter ligation. Following this step, platform-specific adapters are ligated to both ends of the DNA fragments. These adapters contain sequences essential for binding dual-barcoded libraries to a flow cell for sequencing.

Furthermore, DNA amplification was done by 4 cycles of PCR with the addition of HiFi PCR master mix and Primer mix. The amplified products were then purified using 1X AMPure XP beads (Catalog: A63881, Beckman Coulter) and the final DNA library was eluted in 15 μ l of 0.1X TE buffer.

- * Adapter sequences used for preparation of library:
 P7 adapter: read1 AGATCGGAAGAGCACACGTCTGAACTCCAGTCA
 P5 adapter: read2 AGATCGGAAGAGCGTCGTGTAGGGAAAGAGTGT

The library concentration was determined in a Qubit.3 Fluorometer (Catalog: Q33216, Life technologies using The Qubit dsDNA HS (High Sensitivity) Assay Kit (Catalog: Q32854, ThermoFisher Scientific). The Qubit™ 1X dsDNA

HS Assay Kit. DNA HS Assay Kit contains High Sensitivity DNA reagent as well as buffers and two DNA standards. DNA HS assay reagent is one of the most sensitive detection dyes for the accurate quantitation of DNA/library in solution, with linear fluorescence detection in the range of 10 pg/μl to 100 ng/μl of DNA.

Dye and the buffers were diluted at 1:200 ratio and 1 μl of the library was mixed with the dye mix and incubated at RT for 2 min and the readings were taken in the Qubit.3 Fluorometer (Catalog: Q33216, Life technologies). Prior to the sample's measurement, the instrument was calibrated using the two standards provided in the kit.

2.4. Library Validation and next generation sequencing of metagenomes

Quality assessment of the WGS library was done using Agilent D5000 Tape Screen System in a 4150 Tape Station System (Catalog: G2992AA, Agilent) which is designed for analyzing DNA molecules from 35 to 1000 bp. 1 μl of the purified library was mixed with 10 μl of D5000 sample buffer and vortex using IKA vortexer at 2000 rpm for 1 min and spun down to collect the sample to the bottom of the strip. The strip was then loaded on the Agilent 4150 Tape Station system. All the three metagenome samples SA1, SA2 and SA3, were subjected to NGS, and the sequence data was generated using Illumina NovaSeq 6000. The library validation report is presented in Table S2.

2.5. Sequence Data QC and De novo assembly

The sequence data was generated using Illumina HiSeq. Data quality was checked using FastQC (<https://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>. Accessed 24 May 2017.) and MultiQC (Ewels et al., 2016) software. The data was checked for base call quality distribution, % bases above Q30, %GC, and sequencing adapter contamination. (Table S3) The sequence data was processed fastp (Chen et al., 2018) to remove adapter sequences and low-quality bases. The quality trimmed reads and were assembled to contigs using Megahit v1.1.3 (D. Li et al., 2015) with k-mer sizes 21, 49, 77, 105, 133 and 141. Contigs less than 200 bp were removed from the assembly. The assembly statistics can be found in Table S4.

2.6. Microbial diversity computation and Bioinformatic analysis.

The trimmed reads were processed using Kraken2, which classifies the reads using k-mer based homology against a data base of sequences (D. Li et al., 2015). The Kraken2 results were visualized using pavian (Bernt et al., 2013) to generate Sankey plots. Krona plots were created using kraken2 results. The assembled contigs were checked for homology against NCBI nt database. Taxonomic distribution of BLAST hit contigs were identified with TaxonKit v0.2.3 (Shen & Xiong, n.d.). The contigs that were annotated against Eukaryotic sequences were removed and remaining were annotated using Prokka v1.14.6 with --metagenome option (Table S5) (Seemann, 2014). KEGG and COG annotations were obtained by submitting the protein sequences of each sample to KAAS (Moriya et al., 2007) and Recognizer respectively (Fig. 4a, 4b and 5).

3. RESULT

3.1 Microbial community structure

3.1.1. Sequencing analysis

In total, 8.21Gb, 17.33Gb and 10.58Gb raw data were generated by Illumina sequencing of the SA1, SA2 and SA3 metagenome, respectively. The total numbers of sequence read obtained were 50.43 million, 111.47 million and 70.09 million for the SA1, SA2 and SA3 metagenomes, respectively with an average read length of 150bp. After read quality control and de novo assembly, 26.85 million, 56.72 million and 34.62 million contigs were generated for all the three samples, respectively. A summary of the metagenome sequence data is presented in table 1.

Table 1. Summary of metagenomic sequencing data.

Sample ID	No. of raw reads	Classified reads	Chordate reads	Artificial reads	Unclassified reads	Microbial reads	Bacterial reads
SA1	26,853,365	8,546,956	626,632	455	18,306,409	7,900,300	6,863,941
SA2	56,720,462	17,839,920	1,013,291	732	38,880,542	16,792,731	14,803,784
SA3	34,628,718	10,885,901	768,000	550	23,742,817	10,093,631	8,803,158

3.1.2. Microbial community at various taxonomic levels

On the basis of taxonomic annotation of predicted ORFs, it's reveals that in all the three soil samples SA1, SA2 and SA3 metagenomes were dominated by the domain Bacteria (65%, 99% and 68.40%), followed by unknown (29%, 0.0020% and 0.21%) (Fig.2). Less than 2.5% ORFs were assigned to Archaea, Viruses and Eukarya. (Fig.S2a and S2b).

Near about 25 phyla were assigned to the predicted ORFs in all the three metagenome and the relative abundance of microbes at phylum level was quite similar except Myxococcota, Bacillota, Mycoplasmatota, Campylobacterota, Fibrobacterota (Fig.3a). Around all the three metagenome most dominated phyla were Pseudomonadota, Actinomycetota, Acidobacteriota, and accounted for approximately 59%, 85% and 81.78 % of the ORFs in the SA1, SA2 and SA3 metagenome respectively. The rest of classified phyla Deinococcota, Chloroflexota, Thermosulfobacteriota, Nitrospirota, Spirochaetota, Armatimonadota, Cynobacteriota, Bdellovibrionota, Dictyoglomota, Elusimicrobiota, Caldisericota, Bacteroidota, Chlorobiota, Gemmatimonadota, Planctomycetota, Verrucomicrobiota, and Candidatus omnitrophota shared nearly 5.3%, 7.87 % and 7.97% ORFs in SA1, SA2 and SA3 metagenome, respectively. Whereas 29%, 0.20% and 0.21% ORFs remained unassigned. The major bacterial orders identified in taxonomic profiling includes Rhizobiales, Burkholderiales, Streptomycetales, Corynebacteriales, Micrococcales, Myxococcales, Propionibacteriales, Pseudomonadales, Solirubacterales, Micromonosporales, Pseudomonocardiale and Rhodospirillales in all the three metagenomes. While bacterial order Bacillales, Oceanospirallales, Xanthomonadales, Alteromonadales, Clostridiales shares approximately 5.39% 2.3% and 3.2% in SA1, SA2 and SA3 metagenome, respectively. (Fig.3b)

All the metagenome were further analyses at genus level and it was detected that Streptomyces, Bradyrhizobium, Conexibacter, Burkholderia, Mycobacterium, Pseudomonas, Mesorhizobium, Nocardioidea, Rhodoplanes, Anaeromyxobacter, Micromonospora, Azospirillum, Nitrospira, Methylobacterium, Pseudolabrys, Thauera, Azoarcus, Cupriavidus, Variovorax, Sorangium, Actinoplanes, Luteitalea, are the common between all the three metagenome and shares approximately 20%, 39% and 40% in SA1, SA2 and SA3, respectively.

Figure 2. Sankey plot visualization of SA1.

Figure 3. The bar graphs representing microbial community composition revealed in the SA1, SA2 and SA3 metagenomes at different taxonomic levels: (a) Phylum, (b) Order, (c) Genus and (d) Species. Microbial taxa showing less than 1% relative abundance are shown as “others” in phylum and order bar graphs, whereas less than 0.5% are presented in the genus and species.

Genera such as *Marinobacter*, *Halomonas*, *Truepera*, *Geoalkalibacter*, *Nitratireductor*, *Nitrosococcus*, *Thioalkalivibrio*, *Alcanivorax* and *Draconibacterium* were also shows >1 % relative abundance in all the three metagenome. Another 13 genera *Ignavibacterium*, *Gemmatirosa*, *Anaerolinea*, *Gemmatimonas*, *Parvibaculum*, *Idiomarina*, *Melioribacter*, *Geobacter*, *Caldilinea*, *Rhodothermus*, *Halanaerobium*, *Sphingomonas*, and *Fulvivirga* were also shows >1% of relative abundance in all the three metagenome (Fig 3c). While approximately 40%, 56% and 54% of metagenomes share other genera in each sample. The detailed study of all three metagenome indicates that the relative abundance of genus *Thalassospira*, *Halanaerobium*, *methanoculleus*, *fibrobacter*, *Eubacterium*, *Halocella*, *Sphaerobacter* were identified exclusively in all the three genomes.

3.1.3. Environmental Microbial function in contaminated soil samples:

The COG functional annotation results are shown in fig. 4a, the most abundant categories in SA1 sample were general function prediction only (86%), translation regulation and biogenesis (46%) and amino acid transport and metabolism (22%). In SA2 samples were general function prediction only (85%), translation regulation and biogenesis (42%) and amino acid transport and metabolism (21%), posttranslational modification and protein turnover, chaperones (20%). While in SA3 sample’s general function prediction only (85%), translation

Figure 4a. The relative abundance of the COG functional categories of three samples SA1, SA2 and SA3.

regulation and biogenesis (48%) and amino acid transport and metabolism (21%), posttranslational modification and protein turnover, chaperones (20%), etc.

Current study also deals with three major domains such as (Metabolism, molecular function and processing followed by cellular processing and signaling) (Fig.4b). Except from poorly characterized function (7%), in SA1 sample the major 3 GO terms in Metabolism was amino acid transport and metabolism (1,194), energy production and conservation (1,020) and Lipid transport and metabolism (884); among the molecular function and processing the top three were translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis (1,181), Transcription (758) and Replication, recombination and repair (390); and among cellular processing and signaling, the top three were signal transduction and mechanism (675), posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones (512) and cell wall/ membrane/ envelope biogenesis (390). Whereas in SA2 sample, Except from poorly characterized function (9%), the top 3 GO term in Metabolism was amino acid transport and metabolism (14,116), energy production and conservation (11,420) and Lipid transport and metabolism (10,045); among cellular processing and signaling, the top three were signal transduction and mechanism (8,795), posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones (5,730) and cell wall/ membrane/ envelope biogenesis (5,724); and among the molecular function and processing the top three were translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis (9,700), Transcription (8,548) and Replication, recombination and repair (4,201).

Whereas in SA3 sample, except from poorly characterized function (7%), the top 3 GO term in Metabolism was amino acid transport and metabolism (2,394), energy production and conservation (2,159) and Lipid transport and metabolism (1,802); among cellular processing and signaling, the top three were signal transduction and mechanism (1,353), posttranslational modification, protein turnover, chaperones (983) and cell wall/ membrane/ envelope biogenesis (873); and among the molecular function and processing the top three were translation, ribosomal structure and biogenesis (2,086), Transcription (1,360) and Replication, recombination and repair (795), etc.

Figure 4b. The GO distribution analysis of three samples SA1, SA2 and SA3.

The functional analysis of metagenome shows in the SA1 soil sample, the gene related to the metabolism (36.40%) were the most abundant and followed by Brites Hierarchies (30.06%), Genetic information processing (8.43%), Unclassified genes (6.34%), Human disease (5.91%), Environmental information and processing (5.11%), Cellular processing (4.54%) and Organismal system (3.17%). The bar graph in Fig.5 represents the number of gene annotated in each metabolic pathway. The detailed analysis of metabolism, it showed that the most abundant was carbohydrate metabolism (24.55%), followed by amino acid metabolism (21.98%), Energy metabolism (14.25%), Metabolism of cofactors and vitamins (9.6%), etc. Similarly, for the SA2 samples the most abundant metabolic function was metabolism (33.26%) followed by Brites Hierarchies (32.80%), Genetic information processing (8.25%), Unclassified genes (7.37%), Human disease (6.18%), Environmental information and processing (5.73%), Cellular processing (3.88%) and Organismal system (2.48%).

In metabolism, the most abundant was carbohydrate metabolism (21.83%), followed by amino acid metabolism (18.27%), Energy metabolism (13.33%), Metabolism of cofactors and vitamins (11.49%). Similarly, in SA3 sample the most abundant metabolic function was metabolism (34.81%) followed by Brites Hierarchies (28.76%), Genetic information processing (11.50%), Human disease (7.15%), Environmental information and processing (5.09%), Cellular processing (4.54%), Unclassified genes (3.32%), and Organismal system (3.02%). In metabolism, the Carbohydrate metabolism (22.91%) was the most abundant followed by amino acid metabolism (20.11%), Energy metabolism (15.15%), Metabolism of cofactors and vitamins (9.93%), etc.

Figure 5. The number of the genes annotated at the first two levels of KEGG analysis of SA1, SA2 and SA3.

4. DISCUSSION

Discharging of industrial waste, including solid, liquid and gaseous pollutant plays major role in deterioration of our environment. Industrial waste and other pollutant have adverse effect on soil microbial community and natural environment (Verma & Sharma, 2020). Previous works have analyzed soil microbial community of different soils contaminated with different pollutants in the last past years, indicating the presence of diverse microbial population in each soil, contaminated with different pollutants such as hydrocarbons, heavy metals and many more undergoes changes in microbial community structure as well (Banerjee et al., 2011; Bonomo et al., 2022a; Joynt et al., 2006). The bacterial diversity from different sites are depends of the type of sources and the soil properties (Máthé et al., 2012), and reveals that how different pollutants affects the activity and diversity of endogenous microbiota, and the structure of microbial community. This is the first report for a metagenomic study of industrial effluent contaminated soil samples from various dumpsites across, Silvassa, Dadra & Nagar Haveli, UT of DD & DNH, India.

The microbial diversity at the phylum level of all the three metagenomes were analyzed and the data indicates that the dominant phyla were Pseudomonadota, Actinomycetota, Bacillota, Myxococcota, Acidobacteriota and Thermodesulfobacteriota (Fig. 3a,6 and Fig.S3a). It has been reported that the Pseudomonadota was the major dominating phyla in soil microbial diversity of different industrial waste such as from waste water treatment plant, pharmaceuticals, petroleum refinery and tannery waste (Liang et al., 2016; Ma et al., 2018). Similar kind of finding were also reported in microbial diversity study of petrochemical contaminated soils (Eze, 2021; J. W. Kim et al., 2021; Peng et al., 2015c; M. Wang, Garrido-Sanz, et al., 2021). Detailed analyses of the dominant phyla Pseudomonadota reveals that the major abundant class were represented by Alphaproteobacteria, Gammaproteobacteria and Betaproteobacteria. It is also demonstrated that the Alphaproteobacteria possess

Figure 6. Krona plot of Sample SA2.

various mechanisms such as bio-absorption, bioleaching, intracellular accumulation, and enzyme catalyzed transformation through which they are able to tolerate heavy metal pollutants (Meenambigai et al., 2016; Sheik et al., 2012). Similarly, significant role of Gammaproteobacteria in sulfide oxidation has been reported (Desta et al., 2014). Betaproteobacteria also are reported for the degradative potential for various aliphatic and aromatic compounds, embarking their crucial role in bioremediation (Desta et al., 2014). Actinomycetota is one of another major phyla demonstrated in soil samples of the current study, has already been reported for chemical oxygen demand (COD) removal, ammonia oxidation, industrial wastewater treatment, and degradation of aromatic compounds and organic matters (Desta et al., 2014; Liang et al., 2016).

Bacillota is the third highest abundant phylum present in the microbial community structure in the present study. The detailed study of phylum reveals the dominance of Bacilli, Clostridia and Tissierellia, in all the three metagenomes. Members of these phylum acquire sporulation ability, making them more resistant to the various kinds of factors, such as resistant to various pollutants, hyper salinity and low oxygen level in soil as well as in water system (Liang et al., 2016; Ma et al., 2018). Literature also indicates the role of members of this phylum, in the degradation of different aromatic hydrocarbons (Dong et al., 2011).

It was observed that, all the three metagenome SA1, SA2 and SA3 derived from microbiome analysis through NGS, showed dominance of genera including Streptomyces, Bradyrhizobium, Conexibacter, Burkholderia, Mycobacterium, Pseudomonas, Mesorhizobium, Nocardioides, Rhodoplanes, Anaeromyxobacter, Micromonospora, Azospirillum and others. Apart from these some others like Marinobacter, Halomonas, Bacillus, Truepera, Geoalkalibacter and Draconibacterium (Fig3c and FigS3a, b). Similar findings have been reported previously, where soil contaminated with hydrocarbons have some of the major families identified in this study as the most abundant family, which reveals that the bacteria in these families may be associated with the degradation of hydrocarbons (Bao et al., 2017; Bonomo et al., 2022a; Gałazka et al., 2018). Azospirillum is one of the most abundant bacteria in the soil which is also known for their plant growth promoting potentials and widely studied genera (Steenhoudt & Vanderleyden, 2000). Earlier study also indicated the potential of Azospirillum, to degrade hydrocarbons and are capable to remove sulfides from swine waste biogas (Cruz-Hernández et al., 2022; da Silva et al., 2014). It has also been reported that the Pseudomonas, Nitrosococcus, Nitrososphaera, Nitrosomonas and Nitrospira are responsible for the azo dye and hexavalent chromium degradation, ammonia oxidization and nitrification, respectively (Liang et al., 2016, 2017; Ma et al., 2018). Kim et al, used microbial consortium of Brachymonas, Desulfomonas and uncultured Thiobacillus spp. which plays significant role in the denitrification and sulfate oxidization in tannery waste water. There is one another essential genus found in this study, Skermanella spp (I.-S. Kim et al., 2014). This genus is also reported to be involved in pyrene degradation of oilfield soil study, it uses various mechanism such as natural attenuation, bioaugmentation and bio-stimulation (Teng

et al., 2021). Therefore, presence of such genus in these soil study indicates that they could be associated with their roles in biodegradation of crude oil in contaminated soil.

Further, various microbial communities associated with different landfills and such landfills contains high concentration of organic and inorganic compounds and release anthropogenic methane in environment, who also reported that various microbial communities present abundantly in different landfills and are capable to degrading targeted compounds such as Halanaerobium (fermentation of complex organic matter, sulfate-reduction and methanogenesis), Pseudomonas and Acinetobacter (organic matter degradation and mineralization of aromatic compounds), Petrimonas (acetate, hydrogen and CO₂ producers during glucose fermentation), Methanocorpusculum (hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis), they also found that various cellulolytic microbes such as Bacillus, Clostridium, Fibrobacter, Microbacterium, Halocella and Eubacterium were also present in their study (Krishnamurthi & Chakrabarti, 2013; X. Wang et al., 2017; Xu et al., 2017). In the detailed study of microbial metagenome of all the three samples we observed an impressive presence of bacterial groups are already reported, where soil microbial diversity directly collected from oil wells by (Gałazka et al., 2018). Some of the families such as Alphaproteobacteria, Rhizobiaceae, Rhodobacteraceae, Acetobacteraceae and Sphingomonadaceae were present in these samples (Bonomo et al., 2022b). Some of the bacteria which use hydrocarbons as the only source of carbon were also present in this study such as Vibrionaceae, Bacillaceae, Moraxellaceae, Mycobacteriaceae, Sphingomonadaceae, Nocardiaceae and Flavobacteriaceae. We also observed Methylobacteriaceae (which grew methanol and other one carbon compounds as source of carbon and energy) and Geobacteraceae were also present in the metagenomes.

Application of microorganism for the degradation of xenobiotic compounds is one of the most effective methods because it is environmentally friendly approach. There is study conducted by (Cruz-Hernández et al., 2021) were they identified a strain of Microbacterium spp. from burgo soil contaminated with hydrocarbons and these strains are capable to bioremediate such hydrocarbon contaminated soil. Similar kind of Microbial strain were also found in our study. Hence, the abundance of different bacteria genera in this study further corroborates the potential of bacterial genera are capable of utilizing pollutants like Cr, aromatic compounds, organic acids, carbohydrates, amino acids and proteins and are also capable to degradation of petroleum or hydrocarbons in a contaminated environment.

Presence of such potential bioremediating agents in soil samples of Silvassa, a dense forest and hills surrounded area, which is also one of the tribal belts of India, indicates the diversity of soils and their potential applicability to be used in bioremediation of soils. These reported genera can be further explored to check their potential in restoration of soil fertility, as agriculture is the major profession in this tribal region of India.

5. CONCLUSION

In this first of its kind study, in which the microbial diversity of different soils contaminated with industrial effluents through high-throughput metagenomic sequencing. The results shows that all the three samples have unique microbial community structural and functional diversity. The presence of vast microbial diversity representing Pseudomonadota, Actinomycetota, Bacillota, Myxococcota, Acidobacteriota and Thermodesulfobacteriota indicates that presence of these microbes might be involved in biodegradation of various pollutants present in these industrial effluent contaminated soils, of Silvassa region, one of the major tribal belts of India. The presence of aromatic compounds degraders such as (Bacillus, Clostridium and Candidatus Entothionella), chromium and azo dye degraders (Pseudomonas, Meiothermus and Melioribacter), sulfate reducers (Halanaerobium and Desulfuromonas) and the presence of anaerobically aromatic compound degraders (Azoarcus spp.) suggest that the presence of such microbial communities have capabilities of biodegradation of such pollutants. The functional diversity of microbial community was done using COG and KEGG. The detailed analysis of functional categories of genomes reveals that the presence of various genes and enzyme which are responsible for various metabolomic activities which helps in the biodegradation of various pollutant. Hence, isolation and further characterization of various microbial enzyme and proteins can help to assessing the utility of these enzymes towards the development of enzymatic biodegradation technology. This study also provides many drafts genomes and the genome annotation information, which further requires in depth study of microbial ecology. Further exploration of these sequences and their applicability, shall be opening new horizons of research towards sustainable development in this tribal region of India.

6. DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The authors have no conflicts of interest.

7. SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Figure S1. Combine Gel run image of All the three samples SA1, SA2 and SA3.

Table S1. Showing the DNA concentration of the samples SA1, SA2 and SA3.

Table S2. Library Validation report of All the three samples SA1, SA2 and SA3.

Table S3. Summary of sequence data and QC of all three samples.

Table S4. Summary of assembled genome of all the three samples SA1, SA2 and SA3

Table S5. Summary of Prokka annotation of all the three samples SA1, SA2 and SA3.

Figure S2a. Sankey plot of SA2

Figure S2b. Sankey plot of SA3

Figure S3a. Krona plot of SA1

8. NGS DATA AVAILABILITY

All the 3 raw paired end metagenomic data were submitted in the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) Sequence Read Archive (SRA) under accession numbers **SAMN40281360** (SA1 soil sample), **SAMN40281361** (SA2 soil sample), **SAMN40281362** (SA3 soil sample). The metagenomic sequence data is under NCBI Bioproject number **PRJNA1084772**.

9. CREDIT AUTHORSHIP CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

Bariya Nipun: Conceptualization, Visualization, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis Resources. **Mayuri Dholaria:** Supervision, reviewing, Project administration. **Aparna J Tailor:** Review & editing, Data curation, Validation.

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ABBREVIATIONS LIST

CO₂- Carbon dioxide

COD- Chemical Oxygen Demand

COG- Cluster of Orthologous Groups

DD- Diu and Daman

DNA- Deoxyribo Nucleic Acid

D&NH – Dadra and Nagar Haveli

ds – Double stranded

Fig. – Figure

Gb- Gigabyte

GO- Gene Orthology

KEGG- Kyoto Encyclopedia of Gene and Genome

Ltd.- Limited

ml -Milliliter

NGS- Next Generation Sequencing

nmol – nanomolar

ng- nanogram

nt- nucleotide

ORF - Open Reading Frame

PCR - Polymerase Chain Reaction

pg - Pico gram

Pvt. – Private

rRNA- ribosomal Ribonucleic Acid

RT - Room Temperature

SA1- Sample 1

SA2- Sample 2

SA3 - Sample 3

TE- Tri – EDTA

UT - Union Terotory

WGS - Whole Genome Sequencing

µl- Microliter

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Figure S1. Comparative Gel run of all three samples SA1, SA2 and SA3.

Table S1. Showing the DNA concentration of the samples SA1, SA2 and SA3.

DNA quantification tables of all three samples						
Samples details		DNA quantification			Test Results	
S. No	Sample ID	Qubit (ng/μl)	Volume (μl)	Yield (ng)	QC status	Remarks
1.	SA1	8.12	25	203	Pass	
2.	SA2	75	25	1875	Pass	
3	SA3	16.1	25	402.5	Pass	

Table S2. Library Validation report of All the three samples SA1, SA2 and SA3.

Library validation reports of all three samples						
S. No	Sample ID	Lib.Conc. (ng/μl)	Average Size (bp)	Conc. (nmol)	QC status	Remarks
1.	SA1	18.3	334	80.02	Pass	
2.	SA2	9.49	379	37.94	Pass	
3	SA3	17.3	333	78.72	Pass	

Note: The library qualification criteria are based on the presence of a broad peak in the range of 200 bp to 1000 bp, with an average size of 400 bp in the Agilent 4150 TapeStation system and the Qubit concentrations are above 2 ng/μl or 10 nmol.

Table S3. Summary of sequence data and QC of all three samples.

S. No	Sample ID	No. of Reads	Data in (Gbs)	%>=Q30bases	Mean quality score	Read length
1	SA1	54387470	8.21	93.73	35.89	150
2	SA2	114774918	17.33	93.96	35.95	150
3	SA3	70095760	10.53	97.87	35.91	150

Table S4. Summary of assembled genome of all the three samples SA1, SA2 and SA3.

Assembly	SA1	SA2	SA3
Contigs (>=0bp)	210581	1452845	346414

Contigs (>=1000bp)	985	40299	1750
Contigs (>=5000bp)	5	459	19
Contigs (>=10000bp)	2	69	2
Contigs (>=25000bp)	2	3	0
Contigs (>=50000bp)	2	0	0
Largest contig	62835	33914	13573
Total length	82539895	686971264	139128029
GC(%)	68.22	68.06	67.75
N50	376	456	386
N75	333	371	339
L50	86723	517558	140784
L75	145273	937384	237266

Table S5. Summary of Prokka annotation of all the three samples SA1, SA2 and SA3.

Sample ID	CDS	rRNA	Misc_RNA	tRNA	tmRNA	Repeat regions
SA1	21550	136	236	813	6	0
SA2	239724	396	1396	4882	45	4
SA3	43593	148	358	1316	16	0

Figure S2a. Sankey plot of SA2 sample.

Figure S2b. Sankey plot of SA3 sample.

Figure S3a. Krona plot of sample SA1.